

NOTE

Studies on the Tartrate Complex of Nickel

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M. Bobtelsky and C. Heitner¹ studied the tartrate complex of nickel and found that the effect of the ligand increases the absorption of nickel upto a certain concentration beyond which no change occurs for excess amounts. The Nickel tartrate complex has been studied *pH* metrically and the results reported in this paper.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In expt. 1 (results plotted in Fig. 1), 100 ml of a solution containing 0.001250 g mole of tartaric acid and 0.025 g. mole of Potassium nitrate (Curve A) and another solution of

same volume which besides these constituents contain 0.001 g. mole of Nickel sulphate (Curve B) were titrated against 0.1N Sodium hydroxide at 30°.

It is found that the amount of acid liberated is same when the ratio of metal to ligand is increased to 1 : 10. This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 type of complex. The reaction taking place in the expt. 1 is represented by

$$K = \frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Ni}^{++}][\text{H}_2\text{T}]} \quad \dots (1-1)$$

The values of *n* and *K* were calculated according to the method followed in the investigation of Citrate, Tartrate Malate Complexes of Fe(III)². The value of *n* is more than 2 and 3

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1. M. Bobtelsky and Heitner, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1951, 494-502.

2. H. K. Das, G. Mahapatra, R. K. Patnaik and S. Pani, Proceedings of the symposium on the chemistry of co-ordination compound, Part III, pp. 102-126.

above pH 4.2 and 8.6 respectively. Below pH 4.2 the equilibrium constant (K) is calculated according to equation (1-1) and recorded in table 1. The mean value of K is 2.71×10^{-5} .

Above pH 6.5, n is greater than 2. The complex C dissociates like an acid with increasing pH .

$$K_1 = \frac{[C_1^-][H^+]}{[C]} \quad \dots (2-1)$$

The values of this equilibrium constant were calculated according to the method followed in Ferric tartrate complexes and recorded in Table 1. The mean values of K_1 is 3.87×10^{-8} .

Above pH 8.6 n is greater than 3. The complex C_1^- dissociates further to C_2^{--} and a proton according to equation (3)

$$K_2 = \frac{[C_2^{--}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} \quad \dots (3-1)$$

The value of K_2 has been calculated as done earlier and are recorded in Table 1. The mean value is found to be 2.35×10^{-10} .

TABLE 1

pH	$\Delta[NaOH] \times 10^3$	$-\Delta[T] \times 10^4$	$[NiSO_4] \times 10^3$	a/b	$[T]_B \times 10^2$	n	$[C] \times 10^3$	$[Ni^{++}] \times 10^3$	$[H_2T] \times 10^3$	$K \times 10^5$	$K_1 \times 10^8$	$K_2 \times 10^{10}$
3.0	1.947	2.40	9.149	.5753	1.144	.8054	1.477	7.672	4.581	4.200		
3.4	2.32	3.0	8.696	.8770	1.086	1.1740	2.300	6.396	2.108	2.83		
3.8	2.16	2.7	8.375	1.184	1.047	1.4800	3.038	5.337	0.6789	2.11		
4.2	1.52	2.0	8.189	1.482	1.023	1.7037	3.505	4.684	0.1795	1.66		
7.1	2.21	2.82	7.830	1.999	0.9788	2.3530					4.3	
7.7	3.47	4.40	7.696	2.000	0.9620	2.5653					2.59	
8.3	5.41	6.81	7.496	2.00	0.9369	2.9033					4.68	
8.9	7.12	8.88	7.321	2.00	0.9152	3.215						3.45
9.5	8.26	10.33	7.197	2.00	0.8997	3.434						2.42
10.1	9.32	11.63	7.068	2.00	0.8847	3.647						1.45

In the expt. II (Fig. 2) the curve represents the pH titration of 100 ml of a solution containing 0.00125 g. mole of Nickel sulphate and 0.025 g. mole of potassium nitrate against 0.1M sodium tartrate at 30° .

In this experiment the reaction is represented by the equation (4)

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^{-}][\text{H}^{+}]}{[\text{Ni}^{++}][\text{T}^{-}]} \quad \dots (4-1)$$

The proton is removed by C_1^{-} in forming a neutral complex C. Most of the tartrate ions will be removed by nickel ion in forming the complex. Hence very little amount of tartrate will be available for the removal of hydrogen ion.

Above the 1 : 1 inflection point P, the concentration of Ni^{++} can be neglected. The neutral complex C dissociates to C_1^{-} and a proton.

The values of K_1 were calculated by the equation (2-1) at different pH values according to the method followed in the Copper tartrate complex³. The values are tabulated in the Table 2 and the mean value of K_1 is found to be 6.31×10^{-8} . The value is nearly similar to that obtained in the experiment I.

TABLE 2

pH	$[\text{T}] \times 10^2$	$[\text{NiSO}_4] \times 10^2$	$[\text{HT}]^{-} \times 10^3$	$[\text{C}_1]^{-} \times 10^4$	$[\text{C}] \times 10^2$	$K_1 \times 10^8$
5.34	1.304	1.806	1.354	1.410	1.072	6.01
5.35	1.379	1.077	1.835	1.894	1.058	8.00
5.36	1.453	1.069	2.83	2.345	1.046	9.81

Below the inflection point P, the formation of the complex is not complete. The values of K_3 are calculated as done in the Copper tartrate³ and Cobalt citrate⁴ complexes and are tabulated in the Table 3. The mean value of K_3 is 3.99×10^{-5} .

3. R. K. Patnaik and S. Pani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 953.

4. R. K. Patnaik and S. Pani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 364.

TABLE 3

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[NiSO ₄] $\times 10^2$	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^5$	[C] $\times 10^3$	[Ni ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[T ⁻⁻] $\times 10^4$	K ₃ $\times 10^5$
5.46	.9902	1.238	0.6036	9538	0.8547	11.52	1.200	2.39
5.39	1.961	1.226	1.223	1.638	1.725	10.52	2.071	3.06
5.32	3.847	1.201	2.302	2.800	3.463	8.50	3.318	4.74

It can be shown that $\frac{K_3 K_1 K_2}{K_1} = K$. By substitution the value of $\frac{K_3 K_1 K_2}{K_1}$ and

K are found to be 6.98×10^{-5} and 3.99×10^{-5} respectively. The values are nearly the same.

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